

The CO₂NE sampler.

Filling the cone with CO₂.

Scooping the arthropods on the water surface.

Arthropod density in three lowland rice varieties determined by FARMCOP and CO₂NE insect samplers,^a IRR1, 1984.

Sampler	Arthropods (no./5 hills on indicated variety)											
	Brown planthopper <i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>			Green leafhopper <i>Nephotettix</i> spp.			Green mirid bug <i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>			Wolf spider <i>Lycosa pseudo-annulata</i>		
	IR22	IR28	IR36	IR22	IR28	IR36	IR22	IR28	IR36	IR22	IR28	IR36
FARMCOP	7.2 a	4.0 a	1.6 a	44 a	2.8 a	13.6 a	17.6 a	12.2 a	8.4 a	9.2 a	6.4 a	5.2 a
CO ₂ NE	5.2 a	4.8 a	3.2 a	21 b	4.4 a	15.6 a	22.8 a	17.2 a	13.6 a	9.2 a	8.4 a	7.6 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different according to t-test (P < 0.01).

The CO₂ NE sampler is inexpensive and easy to handle. A tank containing 22.5 kg of CO₂ costs about \$10 and is enough to sample 2,000 or more hills. In the field, a portable tank with 300 ml of CO₂, can be used to sample 30 to 40

hills.

In a field trial comparing the CO₂NE and a formerly used FARMCOP suction machine, there was almost no difference in the number of arthropods collected (see table).¹

Brown shield bug attack on rice

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A pentatomid or shield bug damaged rice in Dinajpur District, West Bengal, in 1983. Dinajpur is between 25.2° and 26.5°N and 88° and 89° E. Wet season lowland rice is the principal crop, but summer and pre-kharif rice crops are increasing.

Two species of the pentatomid bug were identified by the Zoological Survey of India, Calcutta, as *Dolycoris indicus* Stal and *D. baccarum* Linn (see figure). Nymphs and adults damage rice by sucking plant sap and milk from panicles in dough stage. Panicle sterility averaged 10%. Populations were highest in Apr, when it was not unusual to find 2-3 insects per plant.¹

Rice hispa in Burdwan, West Bengal

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Rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* occurs

in only a few areas of West Bengal. In 1984 kharif there was a severe hispa outbreak on 62,341 ha of rice in 5 southern districts.

Data from Burdwan District, which had 24,575 ha attacked by hispa, showed 4 broods during 1984 kharif. The first developed just after

transplanting in mid-Aug, the second in the first week of Sep, the third in mid-Sep, and the fourth (only on late-transplanted crops) in the first week of Oct.

Periodic incidence of adults on the leaves indicated successive broods. Grubs mined between the leaf epidermis, turning 1/3 to 1/2 white. At late-stage infestation, fields developed a blighted

look. Early generations caused patchy damage but cumulative damage by successive generations covered whole fields. Crop-cuts (10 m²) were taken from short-duration Ratna and long-duration Pankaj. Yield loss was 23% for short-duration and 17% for long-duration varieties.

Weather conditions may have encouraged the hispa outbreaks. Most

days were rainy during sowing, which prevented the normal dry seeding. Rainfall was higher than normal, but the number of rainy days and the duration of bright sunshine hours were the same. Sunny weather interrupted by quick showers. no summer plowing, and lack of insecticide application may have increased hispa incidence.✍

Virulence of green leafhopper (GLH) colonies from Luzon, Philippines, on IR36 and IR42

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In 1979, we surveyed farmers' fields in the Philippines to determine if there were GLH *Nephotettix virescens* biotypes virulent on the resistant varieties being grown. Results generally indicated that biotypes were not a problem. We repeated the survey in several Luzon provinces in 1984.

GLH adults were collected in Nueva Ecija, Tarlac, Pangasinan, La Union, Ilocos Sur, Ilocos Norte, and Abra and grouped by towns and varieties from which they were collected. Ten colonies were reared on susceptible TN1 in the greenhouse for two generations. A TN1 colony maintained in the greenhouse for more than 50 generations was included in the test. We tested the ability of each colony to develop a population on resistant IR36 and IR42.

Six-day-old seedlings of the test varieties were transplanted at 5 seedlings per pot in 10-cm-diameter clay pots. Two weeks after transplanting, each pot was enclosed in a mylar film cage to keep out other insect pests, parasites, and predators. Ten days later, the plants were inspected and any arthropods present in the cage were removed. Three pair of 3-d-old GLH adults from each of 11 colonies were introduced in each cage, replicated 5 times. The surviving insects were counted 25 d later.

A colony that was significantly bigger than the greenhouse colony on IR36 or IR42 indicated an increase in virulence of that colony (see table). Colonies from all locations except Cuyapo. Nueva

Populations of GLH colonies from Luzon, Philippines, when reared on IR36 and IR42.

Colony	Variety from which collected	Progeny/3 females ^a on	
		IR36	IR42
Capas, Tarlac	IR36	130 abcd	131 ab
Guimba, Nueva Ecija	IR36	164 bcd	204 bc
Cuyapo, Nueva Ecija	IR42	91 abc	178 bc
Umingan, Pangasinan	IR42	152 bcd	127 ab
Santo Tomas-San Jose, Nueva Ecija	IR42	207 d	227 c
Bauang, La Union	IR42, IR36, traditional	143 bcd	472 d
San Fernando-Bacnotan, La Union	IR36, IR42, traditional	109 abc	221 c
Santa Cruz-Bantay, Ilocos Sur	IR42, traditional	176 cd	162 bc
Paoay-Badoc, Ilocos Norte	IR42, Wagwag	152 bcd	155 abc
Pidigan, Abra	IR42	82 ab	184 bc
Greenhouse	TN1	57 a	89 a

^a Separation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

Ecija; San Fernando-Bacnotan. La Union; and Pidigan, Abra, were more virulent on IR36 than the greenhouse colony. On IR42, all colonies except those from Capas, Tarlac; Umingan, Pangasinan; and Paoay-Badoc, Ilocos Norte, were more virulent than the greenhouse colony.

In contrast to our 1979 survey, results indicate that GLH colonies collected in most of the provinces were more virulent than the greenhouse colony.

Populations were about double those of the greenhouse colony on both IR36 and IR42. Therefore, GLH biotypes are developing in the Philippines.

Because IR36 and IR42 have low level of resistance to tungro virus (RTV), but have resistance to the vector GLH, there is the potential for higher RTV incidence on IR36 and IR42 in the locations where GLH colonies are most virulent.✍

Influence of planting time and rainfall on gall midge (GM) incidence and rice yield in Goa, India

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We assessed damage caused by GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) and its impact on grain yield in 1981 and 1982. Jaya was planted at 2-wk intervals in 40-m² plots with 5 replications beginning in Jun and ending in Jul. No insecticide was applied. GM damage was recorded 30, 45, and 60 d after transplanting (DT)

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